

PSYCHOLOGICAL DISTRESS AMONG STAFF NURSES IN SELECTED HOSPITALS OF CEBU PROVINCE: PROPOSED STRESS REDUCTION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

To promote a healthier work environment, investigating the psychological distress among staff nurses in hospitals is necessary. This step enhances the enhance patient care quality and safety, improves workforce retention and productivity, and upholds ethical standards in healthcare delivery. The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between psychological distress and sociodemographic traits among nurses working in selected partnered hospitals. With the use of statistical analysis, a correlational research design was employed to look at the relationship between two variables. The Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10) was utilized to measure psychological distress in the respondents using purposeful sampling. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to characterize and ascertain the noteworthy correlation between psychological distress and sociodemographic traits. The findings of the study indicate that only the area of assignment had a significant relationship with psychological distress with emphasizes on the significance of psychological wellbeing as a crucial component of nursing care.

Keywords: *Stress, Psychological Distress, Staff Nurses, Work Environment,*

INTRODUCTION

The demands and pressures faced by nurses in their daily responsibilities can often lead to significant psychological strain, impacting their well-being and ability to provide optimal care.

According to Davey et al. (2019), "Stress is a subjective feeling produced by events that are uncontrollable." Nurses are left with an overwhelming feeling that comes from the inability to manage emotional, mental, or physical pressure.

Environmental factors have been shown to have a significant impact on an individual's stress levels. Beyond the Pandemic, the workload of healthcare professionals had increased tremendously which leads to more pressure on their physical and mental conditions.

At present, Nurses are at a higher risk of psychological distress which is due to the low personnel density and high work demand (Xiao et al., 2022). They are mostly affected by these changes and in return would suffer from burnouts, errors, stress, and fatigue. This leads to a growing concern that psychological distress possesses a threat to the nurses. Psychological distress among nurses often leads to a decline in their performance of their duties thus affecting the entire Health Care Delivery System.

The researchers primarily aimed to associate socio-demographic characteristics and psychological distress among nurses in hospitals of Cebu Province.

Psychological Distress and the Working Environment

Psychological distress is a state of emotional distress experienced when overwhelmed by pressure, often resulting from common mental disorders like anxiety and depression. It is a pressing issue affecting both employees and organizations, with increasing workloads, bureaucracy, loss of autonomy, and toxic working environments being sources of stress. (Riley et al., 2021). Studies have found that psychological discomfort not only affects psychosomatic function and quality of life but also leads to poor job performance and high turnover rates, lowering nursing professionalism and care quality. (Liu et al., 2021) Work-related stress is a global issue that impacts productivity and employee health and well-being. Stress at work occurs when an individual's capacity to cope with job demands exceeds their capacity.

Psychological Distress within Nurses

Healthcare workers, particularly nurses, face significant physical and mental strain due to long shifts and increased workloads during the pandemic. Nurses often experience higher levels of stress, depression, and anxiety due to their heavy workload. The importance of nurses in healthcare delivery cannot be overstated, as job stress negatively impacts their quality of life and performance. (Ghawadra et al., 2019). Work-related psychological

distress can lead to a decline in patient care standards, irritation towards coworkers, cognitive impairments, and job-leaving intentions. A study conducted by Babapour et al. (2022) stated that “Job stress has a negative effect on the quality of life related to nurses’ health. It can also overshadow the performance of care and reduce such behaviors in nurses.”

These negative occupational outcomes can compromise the quality of services and patient care, affecting the overall quality of care provided. Therefore, it is crucial for healthcare workers to address these issues to ensure the well-being of their patients.

According to Bonsaksen et al. (2021), nurses with work-home interaction problems and low job coping have higher psychological distress. Role stress is a widespread phenomenon in the healthcare industry that affects people all over the world. The widespread global lack of nursing staff, which the World Health Organization projects would reach 12.9 million by the year 2035, makes the issue much worse (Xiao et al., 2022).

Socio-demographic Factors and Psychological Stress

Stress is influenced by various factors, including socio-demographic factors. Individuals’ perception of stress and coping mechanisms are influenced by these factors. Among the variables that can influence the development of psychological distress are socio-demographic factors. A person’s demographic factors may shape how one’s perception of stress and their ways of coping (Asturias et al., 2021). According to Liu et al., (2023), they have found out in their study that the number of years of work experience is very significant to psychological discomfort since the more years of experience a person has, the less likely they are to feel it. Other demographic and occupational factors, such as age, sex, employment duration, work hours, education, and professional titles, have been linked to stress or burnout among medical professionals.

Ezenwaji et al. (2019) found that medical professionals often experience work-related stress and burnout, which can be linked to sociodemographic factors such as sex, age, work environment, and work experience. Nurses often face challenging environments, dealing with serious illnesses, complex patient and family situations, and distressed individuals. Additionally, many nurses are overworked, underpaid, undertrained, poorly overseen, and under-resourced. These factors can lead to burnout, emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and low satisfaction with their accomplishments. (Nowacka et al., 2018). The complexity of these factors shapes the character of nursing as a profession that overuses physical and mental capacities.

Theoretical Framework

Psychodynamic Theory by Sigmund Freud

This study uses Sigmund Freud's Psychodynamic Theory to examine the influence of socio-demographic factors on psychological distress in staff nurses. Freud posits that intrapsychic processes and interpersonal patterns, based on childhood experiences, can

explain human behavior. This theory suggests that mental issues can be traced beyond conscious self-control, indicating that external forces play a role in their development.

Erik Erikson's Stages of Psychosocial Development, which include young adulthood (18-35), middle adulthood (35-55), and late adulthood (55-60), outlines different stages of development and age ranges. Failure to reach each stage can lead to psychological complications. Both theories highlight the importance of understanding and addressing external factors in shaping human behavior.

Patricia Benner's Novice to Expert Theory is a framework that describes the stages of skill acquisition and development within a specific practice. It suggests that individuals progress through five levels of expertise: novice, beginner, competent, proficient, and expert. Expertise is not solely determined by years spent in a field but also by the quality and diversity of experiences. In the novice stage, nurses are newcomers with little or no experience, which can affect their ability to cope with new challenges. In the beginner stage, they have gained some experience but still struggle with the overall context. In the competent stage, they have acquired enough experience to accomplish tasks effectively and manage stressors. In the proficient stage, they have developed a holistic understanding of the domain and can make sound judgments. In the expert stage, they possess extensive knowledge and an intuitive understanding of complex situations.

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and psychological distress among staff nurses in selected hospitals of Cebu Province. To achieve this goal, the study will address the following research questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the staff nurses in the selected hospitals?
 - 1.1; Age
 - 1.2; Gender
 - 1.3; Length of Experience
 - 1.4; Marital Status
 - 1.5; Area of Assignment/ Assigned Ward
2. What is the level of psychological distress of nurses in the selected hospitals?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the socio-demographic characteristics and the psychological distress among staff nurses in selected hospitals of Cebu Province?

METHODOLOGY

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual idea illustrates the interrelationship of stress sources, stress status, and stress's impact on mental health. This is a visual concept created by the current researcher to depict the input, process, and output of the research. This study will focus on socio-demographic factors being the independent variable while psychological distress will be the dependent variable.

The researchers attempted to determine the relationship between socio-demographic factors and psychological distress. Moreover, if the outcome of the study suggests that there is indeed a link between socio-demographic factors and psychological distress then recommendations for a stress reduction program will be made by the researchers. This conceptualization is further expanded in the schematic design below:

The study utilized a correlational research design to examine the correlation between sociodemographic factors and psychological distress among staff nurses. Questionnaires were distributed to participants, based on their prior knowledge of these factors. The results were analyzed to determine the relationship between sociodemographic factors and psychological distress, forming the basis for a stress reduction program.

This study aimed to study staff nurses at the selected partnered Hospitals. Participants had to meet two qualifications: to be working at the hospital and understand the tool and consent forms used in the research. The study expected 80 respondents to participate in the survey.

The study used the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale-10 (K10), a standardized questionnaire developed by Professor Ron Kessler and Dan Mroczke, to measure non-

specific psychological distress in the anxiety-depression spectrum. The K10 measures nervousness, agitation, psychological fatigue, and depression over the past four weeks.

Researchers conducted the study on the partnered hospitals obtaining approval. They provided a consent form for respondents, outlining the study's aims, beneficiaries, and risks. Participants were informed that their participation was voluntary and could be declined at any time. The data was only accessible to the researchers, and the paper served as a guide for future student nurse researchers and nursing interventions for stress reduction. The study's confidentiality and anonymity were ensured.

A 10-item questionnaire measures psychological distress by asking about negative emotional states experienced in the four weeks prior to an interview. Each question has a five-level response scale based on the duration of the experience.

- None of the time
- A little of the time
- Some of the time
- Most of the time
- All of the time

The scores range from 1 to 5, with low scores indicating low levels of distress and high scores indicating high levels. The K10 results are commonly grouped for output.

Table 1. Interpretation Guide for Psychological Distress.

Range of Score	Interpretation
30 – 50	Very High
22 – 29	High
16 – 21	Moderate
10 – 15	Little or no psychological distress

The study uses the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale-10 (K10) as part of a research instrument, based on previous studies. The K10, which measures psychological distress, has a high level of distress, suggesting a need for professional help. The questionnaire, created using Google Forms, includes items about the respondents' socio-demographic profile and the K10, demonstrating strong construct validity and reliability.

Researchers used purposive sampling to gather data from staff nurses in selected Cebu Province hospitals. After receiving permission, they conducted an online survey using

Google Forms. The questionnaires included an informed consent form for respondents to ensure their legal rights. The survey was distributed to the hospital head via email, and the data was collected, organized, and summarized using Google Forms and Microsoft Excel for interpretation and data analysis.

The study used descriptive statistics to describe socio-demographic characteristics and psychological distress levels among staff nurses in Cebu Province hospitals. Inferential statistics, including Chi-squared test and Pearson's value, were used to determine the significant relationship between these factors.

The protocol for this research study was submitted to the University of San Carlos' Research Ethics Committee, receiving Protocol Number: 2023-096. Data collection commenced only after obtaining the board's approval. The researchers underscore that all participants were volunteers, with the right to withdraw from the study at any point if they chose to do so. Participants provided informed consent before participating. All data collected adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The privacy rights of participants were respected, and confidentiality was strictly maintained throughout the study. All information gathered was kept confidential, ensuring participants' anonymity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of Respondents

Table 2. Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Socio-demographic Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age (in years)		
18 - 35	33	47.14%
36 - 55	36	51.43%
56 - 65	1	1.43%
Gender		
Male	18	25.71%
Female	52	74.29%
Length of experience		
1 - 11 months	5	7.14%
1 - 2 years	11	15.71%
3 - 5 years	18	25.71%
6 - 10 years	16	22.87%
More than 10 years	20	28.57%
Marital status		
Single	32	45.71%
Married	37	52.86%
Widowed	1	1.43%
Area of assignment		
Medical Ward	6	8.57%
OB Ward	12	17.14%
NICU	10	14.29%
ICU	11	15.71%
ER	17	24.29%
LRDR	9	12.86%
Others	5	7.14%

The majority of respondents in the survey were aged 18-35, with 51.43% aged 36-55 and 1.43% aged 55-65. This indicates that most staff nurses are young adults, with some having less than 10 years of experience. Workplace stress is a significant challenge, with younger people emerging as the most stressed demographic in the workplace. This is attributed to the pressure to succeed, and the higher stress levels associated with the younger generation. It indicates that younger people are emerging as the most stressed demographic in the workplace, and struggling mightily to cope. In relation to this, younger people have higher stress levels which is related to the pressure to succeed. (McManus et al., 2008).

The survey revealed that 74.29% of respondents are female.

This shift towards gender equity in the healthcare industry has been significant, but it also raises concerns about psychological suffering. A study of 259 nursing research journals found a persistent bias in favor of female participants, with 75.3% of participants being female and 38% having all-female samples. This bias is observed regardless of funding source, methodological features, or researcher characteristics. Nurse researchers should consider who benefits from their research and if they are missing out on specific benefits.

The majority of respondents (45.71%) are single, with 52.86% being married and 1.43% being widowed. While marital status can provide emotional support, responsibility sharing, and community, its effect on psychological well-being may vary depending on the relationship, personal coping strategies, and life circumstances. Comprehensive examinations of various aspects are preferable for understanding and treating psychological suffering. The association between marital quality and job satisfaction highlights the need for Chinese nurse managers to consider marital quality as an important factor in improving nurses' job satisfaction. Balancing work and married life could positively impact nurses' job satisfaction. (Ouyang et al., 201).

The table shows the percentage of nurses with varying lengths of experience, with 7.14% having 1-11 months, 15.71% having 1-2 years, 25.71% having 3-5 years, 22.87% having 6-10 years, and 28.57% having more than 10 years. Experienced nurses are considered the best in providing care and handling patients, resulting in shorter stays. However, nurses with 5-10 experiences are more likely to experience emotional exhaustion and burnout due to heavy workload, interpersonal relationships, and physician-patient relations. Qu, H., & Wang, C. (2022).

These nurses are at a turning point in their lives, focusing on family, work, and promotions. With their experience and knowledge, experienced nurses function more effectively and deliver the best care for patients, which new nurses can still learn. Despite the stressful job, accumulated work experiences help manage problems and gradually decrease pressure over time.

Lastly, the table shows that the majority of respondents are from the Emergency Room, with 8.57% from the Medical Ward, 17.14% from the Obstetric Ward, 14.29% from the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit, 15.71% from the Intensive Care Unit, 24.29% from the Emergency Room, 12.86% from the Labor Room and Delivery Room, and 7.14% from other areas of the hospital. Hospital nurses are generally at a higher risk of stress due to their shifts and the different wards/departments that serve specific patient services. (Muhamad Robot et al., 2021). The stress level varies between departments, with emergency departments often experiencing the most stress. (Mahmood et al., 2020).

Table 3. The Level of Psychological Distress among Staff Nurses

NURSES	K-10 Score (Average)	Level of distress
1. Age (in years)		
18 - 35	18.39	Moderate
36 - 55	16.92	Moderate
56 - 65	10.00	Little / No psychological distress
2. Gender		
Male	17.33	Moderate
Female	17.58	Moderate
3. Length of experience		
1 - 11 months	15.40	Little / No psychological distress
1 - 2 years	14.64	Little / No psychological distress
3 - 5 years	19.50	Moderate
6 - 10 years	18.75	Moderate
More than 10 years	16.85	Moderate
4. Marital status		
Single	18.63	Moderate
Married	16.76	Moderate
Widowed	10.00	Little / No psychological distress
5. Area of assignment		
Medical Ward	14.17	Little / No psychological distress
OB Ward	15.92	Moderate
NICU	19.20	Moderate
ICU	19.45	Moderate
ER	18.29	Moderate
LRDR	18.56	Moderate
Others	13.20	Little / No psychological distress
OVERALL (All nurses)		
	17.51	Moderate

The table shows that nurses in healthcare facilities are at high risk for stress, with most experiencing mild to moderate stress as supported by a study conducted by Oktovin et al (2021).

The age range of 18-35 years old has the highest score with moderate distress, suggesting that younger nurses experience more distress due to less clinical experience and a lack of coping skills to counter the stress associated with clinical work. (Slykerman et al., 2021).

Gender differences in mental health among nurses are minimal, with females experiencing a slight higher prevalence of psychological distress. Although males may have higher rates of mental health disorders, this difference is not evident as both genders reported a small difference in their K-10 scores. (Mercy Idowu et al., 2022).

Nurses with over 10 years of experience more distress than new nurses. This suggests that the healthcare system needs to consider factors such as reasonable staffing, working hours, promotion systems, job stress causes, job content clarification, and practical work shift scheduling to ensure a healthy workforce. (Huang et al. 2016).

Single individuals experience higher levels of distress and anxiety compared to married individuals, with a higher score in the marital status scale. Previous research has shown that single individuals report higher levels of depression, anxiety, mood disorders, adjustment problems, and alcohol-related issues. (Braithwaite et al. 2010).

The Intensive Care Unit area has the highest score of distress, indicating that nurses assigned to this area experience higher levels of psychological distress, anxiety, trauma, and secondary traumatic stress. This is due to the high-risk environment, high stress, and burnouts associated with their job. (Foley et al., 2022). However, there is a small difference in their K-10 scores due to the nature of their work environment, which is influenced by the ward they are assigned to.

Table 4. Relationship between Socio-demographic Characteristics and Psychological Distress among Nurses

Socio-demo characteristic		Psychological Distress	Interpretation
1. Age	Chi-square value p-value	0.848 0.6544	No significant relationship between age and psychological distress
2. Gender	Chi-square value p-value	1.122 0.5706	No significant relationship between gender and psychological distress
3. Length of experience	Chi-square value p-value	4.949 0.1756	No significant relationship between length of experience and psychological distress
4. Marital status	Chi-square value p-value	2.946 0.2292	No significant relationship between marital status and psychological distress
5. Area of assignment	Chi-square value p-value	9.379 0.0247	There is a significant relationship between area of assignment and psychological distress

NOTE: When p-value < 0.0.05, a significant relationship exists between variables

Table 4 reveals a lack of significant relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and psychological distress. Age, gender, experience, marital status, and area of assignment were not found to contribute to psychological distress. This finding agrees with the existing evidence from a study by Nieuwoudt (2021),

Gender with a p-value of (0.5706), it indicates that there is also no relationship between gender and psychological distress which means that gender does not promote psychological distress. Although, another study by Zhang et al. (2018),

This contradicts a study by Nieuwoudt (2021) which found no significant relationship between age, stress, gender, and psychological distress. Gender also showed no relationship with psychological distress, contradicting Zhang et al. (2018)'s suggestion

that it is moderated by gender. Ochilbek et al (2020) found females at a higher risk of psychological distress than males, but this was difficult to agree with due to small differences in K-10 scores.

The study found a negative correlation between nurses' length of experience and psychological distress, with a p-value of 0.1756. This contradicts previous studies by Belay et al (2020) and Kabito & Wami (2020), which found work experience to be significantly associated with psychological distress. Additionally, Kabito & Wami (2020) found that teaching experience was significantly associated with stress.

The study found no significant relationship between marital status and psychological distress among respondents. However, a study by Grundström et al. (2021) found that single, divorced, and widowed individuals have poorer mental well-being compared to married individuals. The relationship can vary depending on relationship nature, personal coping strategies, and life circumstances. Previous research (Hsu & Barrett, 2020) suggests that married individuals experience higher well-being than those who are never married, but this literature focuses more on the negative dimension.

Finally, the area of assignment resulted in a p-value of (0.0247). This means that it is a positive correlation which indicates that there is a significant relationship between the area of assignment and psychological distress. The study by Nwadula (2022) found a significant positive correlation between the area of assignment and psychological distress among nurses. Factors such as short-staffed nurses, toxic work shifts, intense workloads, and work environments contribute to distress and burnout among nurses. The study also found that the area of assignment had a significant relationship with psychological distress among nurses. To reduce the likelihood of psychological distress and burnout among nurses, good management, stress reduction programs, sufficient staff, and problem-focused coping strategies can be implemented. Over time, these issues can be managed and prevented with proper interventions.

Conclusions

The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and the psychological distress among staff nurses in selected hospitals in Cebu Province as the basis for a proposed stress program. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following profiles of the participants in terms of Age, Gender, Length of experience, Marital Status, and Area of Assignment.

Based on the results, the major findings of this study are as follows:

1. Out of 70 respondents, the majority were within age of 36-55 years old giving a count of 1.43% and 18-35 years old were 41.14%. While only 1.43% of the respondents were within the age range of 55-65 years old. There were 74.29% female participants and 25.71% male participants. The majority of marital status are married with 52.86% and

45.71% were single. While only 1.43% of the respondents were widowed. Most of the respondents of length of experience were more than 10 years with 28.57%, followed by 25.71% of 3-5 years of experience, 6-10 years of experience with 22.87%, and 1-2 years of experience with 15.71%. While only 7.14% of the respondents were within 1-11 months of experience. There were 24.29% respondents from the ER, 17.14% from the OB ward, 15.71% from the ICU, 14.29% from the NICU, 12.86% from the LRDR, 8.57% from the Medical Ward, and 7.14% from other areas of the hospital.

2. With a K10 average score of 17.51 in the level of psychological distress among staff nurses, the perceived average indicates that there is a moderate level of distress. Out of 70 respondents, 46% of the sample population experienced moderate level of distress.

3. There is a significant relationship between the area of assignment and psychological distress which was proven by its p-value of (0.0247). This indicates that the nurse's psychological distress is affected by their area of assignment. On the other hand, the remaining socio-demographic characteristics in terms of age, gender, length of experience, and marital status resulted with p-values of (0.6544), (0.5706), (0.1756), and (0.2292) indicating a negative correlation between the variables.

Recommendations

The study aims to understand the factors contributing to nurses' psychological distress, a prevalent issue in the nursing profession, and recommends solutions.

The study recommends that respondents with moderate-high psychological distress engage in activities to manage and reduce their distress, including incorporating relaxing techniques. After approval, the study results will be sent to the respondents' hospitals, along with a stress reduction program attached. The program is also included in Appendix D - Proposed Stress Reduction Program.

Researchers recommend developing a stress reduction program to selected hospitals, focusing on the psychological distress of nurses. The program is digitally disseminated through a poster, highlighting the importance of integrating appropriate techniques for managing workplace stress. The researchers have coordinated with institutional heads to promote the program and emphasize the significance of integrating appropriate techniques for managing psychological distress in the workplace. This will contribute to supporting mental health.

Researchers recommend that Healthcare institutes should implement monthly mental health check-ups for their personnel to improve psychological conditions and benefit the institute.

Researchers recommend that Future researchers should conduct larger sample sizes and conduct research in more hospitals to expand the scope and gather more information

on socio-demographic characteristics and psychological distress among staff nurses, thereby enhancing the scope of their study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study was conducted without penalty for voluntary participation, adhering to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 and maintaining participant privacy. Researchers kept participant responses private and shared them with advisors. Non-participation was not used against participants or others. Consenting participants had the right to withdraw or withhold information and could stop at any time if they experienced discomfort. The protocol was submitted to the University of San Carlos' Research Ethics Committee, receiving Protocol Number: 2023-096. Data collection began after board approval. Participants provided informed consent and their privacy rights were respected, with confidentiality strictly maintained throughout the study.

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